

PAPER D: REVIEW ARTICLE

Prospects of Alternative Energy Harvest from Placenta Degradation

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Abstract

Globally, the first use of placentas to generate energy was at Perpetual Succor Hospital, Cebu City, Philippines. Currently, placentas are objects of rituals in many countries of the world. They are either planted beside trees of attached significance to the family or consumed in some instances. This study examines this practice, and its alternative channeling into digesters to produce bioenergy. Previous research on biodigesters constructed near Mwananyamala Regional Hospital, Tanzania and the Bir Hospital, Kathmandu, Nepal, generates 2.5 m³ and 5.78 m³ respectively of biogas daily from co-digestion of placenta and food waste. Its main use is to power the healthcare facility and generate gas to boil water needed by patients. But the utilization of placentas as sole biogas feedstock for energy generation hasn't been carried out.

External Link:

Keywords: Placenta, Bioenergy, Medical waste, Biogas, Biodegradable waste, Anaerobic digestion

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1.0. | Introduction

In Greek, a complex, temporary organ called placenta implies a 'flat cake', which serves as a site for physiological exchanges between a mother and her embryo/fetus [1, 2]. It is a fascinating endocrine organ of a viviparous organism that is connected to the fetus by the umbilical cord, that is composed of closely apposed maternal and fetal tissues [1–3]. Medically, the organ is a surrogate or provisional respiratory (lungs), excretory (kidney), endocrine glands, immunity, protection and digestive organ (gut, liver, intestine) that permits the entry of nutrients in form of food and vitamins, hormones, oxygen and antibodies to the developing embryo of a mother, and takes out nitrogenous metabolic waste and carbon dioxide [1, 2, 4–7]. The six functions it performs is basically, endocytosis and catabolism of maternal proteins, antithrombotic activity, metabolic regulation and ionic homeostasis, active transport of amino acids and other nutrients, excretion of waste products and the secretion of steroid, peptide hormones, cytokines and growth factors [6, 8].

Placentas are classified under biodegradable healthcare waste. They are waste that hasn't been reported to constitute any harm to the environment because adequate disposal measures are voluntarily carried out with little or no enforcement. The placenta is culturally and spiritually valuable to majority of families in different parts of the world. It suffices to say that, the value attached to it, aid significantly in protecting the surrounding. Similar biodegradable waste from agriculture, residential buildings, canteen and industries are feedstock for biogas production. Upgraded biogas can be used as fuel to run vehicles, power electrical generators, generate electricity, produce gas for cooking and lighting. Exploration of all these classes of biodegradable

waste has led to a clean and healthy environment, where harnessed. However, studies on the possibility of utilizing medical waste like body parts, blood, human urine, surgery waste and placenta in particular are rarely conducted. It is logical to build biodigesters near their feedstock source. So, the construction of biogas plants near maternal healthcare institutions can help in solving electricity shortages, most needed by hospitals to function effectively, especially in developing nations.

Therefore, the objectives of this work are to study the function of the placenta, its development and importance to the woman's fetus and whether it is a pollution risk to the environment. Primarily, their biogas potential would be examined from previous studies and the level of attention given to the waste in order to harvest energy from them, is surveyed.

2.1. | Placenta Development

The placenta derives its name from Greek as a result of its relative flatness [1, 6, 7]. A mature human placenta is described as a large disc-like shape discoid organ which is $\cong$ 10-25cm in diameter, 3cm thick and weighs 400-600g [3, 6, 8]. Principal surfaces of a placenta are two; namely, the maternal surface facing the outside and the fetal surface facing the inside or the fetus [6, 7]. They can be classified into four, namely, based on the involvement of embryonic tissue (viz. chorio-vitelline/yolk sac and chorio-allantoic placenta), depending on the distribution of villi on chorion (e.g., diffuse, cotyledonary, zonary, discoidal and metadiscoidal placenta), based on the relationship of villi with the uterine wall (e.g., non-deciduous, deciduous, conta-desiduate placenta) and depending on the degree of involvement of fetal and maternal tissues (viz. uterine and fetal tissue) [1, 6]. Fig. 1 illustrates the various parts of a typical placenta.

Figure 1: A well labelled Placenta [6, 7]

Literature findings reveals that the placenta is susceptible to abnormal growth and function if exposed to air pollution during pregnancy [3]. Development of the placenta entails three key stages starting from pre-lacunar, lacunar and villous stages, according to the same author. The initial step in placenta formation is the implantation of the blastocyst that develops nearly five days post-fertilization [3, 4, 6]. When the baby is a blastocyst (Fig. 2), it eventually gets covered by the uterine wall cells [6]. This encompasses a series of events beginning with apposition, adhesion and invasion, according to Witkin (2005). Hammer & Lelievre (2015) explains that the covered blastocyst then gets detached from the uterine wall due to the contraction and relaxation experienced near the end of pregnancy. After about 15-30 minutes of childbirth, naturally, the placenta comes out and is discarded, consumed or planted by some families.

Figure 2: The Blastocyst [6]

2.1.1. | *Placenta Disposal and Utilization*

The placenta is a pathological clinical waste, which must be discarded at birth, incinerated at high temperature or buried deep down the ground [2, 5, 9]. Alongside this waste, other medical wastes that falls within the definition of pathological waste by the WHO, viz., body parts and fetus must be made to undergo the same disposal measure [10]. Every hospital in Australia had their own protocols and guidelines for managing healthcare waste [2]. In the country, the decision to take a placenta home by a woman is respected, but she must

however sign a placenta release form that stipulates save burial practices to prevent disease spread. The law recognizes the cultural, religious and spiritual sensitivity in doing so, and so sees it as the 'patient needs'. Even though the practice is same in other parts of the world, however, laws are absent to guide such practice [9]. Literature studies shows that, there are four different placenta rituals. They are, medical research donation, placenta burial, placentophagy (eating or consuming the placenta), and lotus birth (i.e., allowing the umbilical cord stay until it dries up and comes out from the newborn naturally) [2, 9, 11]. In a survey conducted by Abudu et al. (2015), only few women in Kwara state, Nigeria are willing to donate their placentas for biomedical research.

Burial ritual of the placenta emerges from 3 believes and perceptions: namely, that the organ is a sacred link of the child to the land, that it is the baby's spirit guide and/or lastly a means to bestow blessings upon the baby [12-14]. Traditional Native Hawaiians, Native Americans, Maori and African tribes practiced ritual burial, believing that it connects the newborn to the earth. The placenta was given the moniker "Our Mother" by the Igbo tribe of Africa because they think that burying it makes a connection between the infant and the underground spirits. According to Navajo belief, burying the placenta on the child's family's tribal land will connect or firmly establish the child's spirit with his ancestors and the land. The Navajo think that by doing this, the youngster will always find his or her way back home. To bind the kid to the land, the Maori people of New Zealand bury the placenta there. Whenua is the equivalent of the Maori word for land and placenta. The placenta is known as "Grandmother" by the Chinook and Quinault Native American tribes. Traditional Hmong, Malaysian, Nepalese, Balinese, Siberian, and Icelanders practiced placenta burial rituals, believing it is the baby's spirit guide [13, 14]. The placenta is buried with great care and ritual in the Hmong home because it is thought to be the spiritual cloak the infant wore to enter this world. The baby's spirit will travel back to the area where the placenta was buried once he or she has passed away to retrieve the placenta after the baby has lived his or her life. The placenta can serve as his spiritual cloak once more, enabling him to return to the other side. The placenta's Hmong name literally translates to "jacket." In Bali, the placenta is referred to as "Ari-Ari" and is said to be the kid's guardian angel's physical body. The angel's spirit remains with the child throughout their life. To be buried, the

placenta is wrapped in fabric and put inside a coconut. Native Icelanders refer to the placenta as the baby's "guardian angel" by the name "fylgia." Traditional Chinese, Indonesian, Mayan, Thai, Ibani, Cambodian, Ukraine, Turks, Japanese and Yugoslavians practiced rituals, taking it as an opportunity to bestow blessing and protection upon the child [12, 14]. Numerous literary and artistic works in China highlight the significance of appropriately disposing of the placenta after childbirth in traditional Chinese culture. The tree the placenta was buried under is revered by the Mayans, who think that because of the spiritual connection made, the tree has the power to protect the kid. A solemn burial ceremony is part of Japanese culture since the placenta was thought to be connected to the future of the child. First, water was used to wash the placenta, and then sake. It was then placed in a wooden box after being wrapped in colored silk cloths. Writing brushes or needles and thread were added as lucky symbols to ensure a prosperous life. Based on the association with both the child and the mother, the placenta, when arranged of disgracefully, was accepted to have a possibly grave impact on long haul destiny of the mother and child, as well as possibly insulting different spirits through the contamination of female blood.

Where those practices are allowed, placentas are encouraged to be stored in an empty refrigerator alone or kept in a container, on ice and in an esky before burial in less than 2-3 hours [9]. The third ritual is the act of encapsulating or eating the placenta. Encapsulation or consumption of the placenta has no proven health benefits to the mother or the family. Majority of placenta taken home are either buried (to portray some spiritual, cultural or personal believes) or consumed. It is always advised to allow health practitioners examine the placenta before taking home, and when it is taken home, it shouldn't be dumped in council or domestic waste bins [9]. The last practice is the lotus birth, which is rarely practiced.

2.2. | Bioenergy Production from Placenta

Currently, the new practice of utilizing human placenta to generate biogas hasn't been given the needed attention. Placenta degradation in biodigester has the potential of replacing some of the disposal rituals embarked upon by some families in some part of the world. It could be tagged the fifth placenta ritual. Energy in form of electricity is needed in health care institutions to create a conducive environment for

patients, prepare foods, refrigerate nutritional drinks, help maintain a hygienic environment in the hospital vicinity and, keep some medicines at the desired temperature. In the developing world, these functions are difficult to carry out due to inadequate electricity.

Anaerobic digestion had become the most attractive and safest technology for biodegradable healthcare waste treatment across the world [10, 15]. As pathological and food waste degrade, the possibility of it causing disease vectors is heightened. Brazil, Philippines, Nepal, and Tanzania are few developing countries that had used placenta to generate biogas energy, either by carrying out research or through the building of biogas plants near hospitals. In Africa, Tanzania is the first country to build a biogas plant, specifically to

produce biogas from placenta. It however remains the only country doing so at the moment in the continent. Honest & Saria (2020) reported that, after a retention time of 18 weeks, 5-33 kPa pressure and 28.7-32.6°C temperature, the brick, waterproof biodigester, constructed at Mwananyamala Regional Hospital, Tanzania, produces 2.5 m³ daily of biogas. The conical bottom spherical shape digester of volume 32 m³ and radius 2.5cm, used at the hospital, digests 1:3 placenta-to-food waste ratio – having separate inlet for the food waste. Successes achieved at Mwananyamala (Fig. 3) and the Ubungo Municipal Hospitals, encourages the Tanzanian government to roll out new construction sites at 10 other Regional referral hospitals, that includes Arusha, Dodoma, Geita, Iringa, Kigoma, Manyara, Mbeya, Mwanza, Njombe and Ruvuma, to use the same feedstock [16].

Figure 3: Hospitals across the World that Built Biogas Plants to Digest Human Placenta

In Southern Brazil, a study conducted by Soares et al. (2020) in Santa Catarina, shows that the addition of porcine placenta to swine manure, reduces inhibitory effects and propel biogas yield by 20%. The decomposition was carried out during the dry season when the temperature is between 16-24°C over a period of 30 days. In Nepal, Rastriya Gobar Gas Company (RGG) constructed a 21 m³ biodigester near the Bir hospital, Mahaboudha, Kathmandu in 2011. The plant is capable of digesting food left overs, cow dung and $\cong$ 5kg of amputated pathological waste [10]. Daily, 95 kg of mixed waste is fed to the digester to produce an average of 5.78 m³/day of biogas. The earliest and arguably the first biogas plant built at close proximity to hospital for biogas production from placenta in the world was suggested by Jared Escarpe in 2010 [18]. Specifically, two plants were constructed at Perpetual Succor Hospital, Cebu City, Philippines at the cost of \$5,950. It co-digest food waste, garden waste and human placenta to generate energy from methane, in order to power the hospital buildings as well as cook food. The plant's construction was coordinated by Health Care Without Harm (HCWH), funded by Global Environment Facility and supported by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP).

3.0. | Conclusion

Possibility of generating bioenergy from placenta fermentation has been successfully studied. Placentas develop gradually in a mother to become a useful backbone for the growth of the unborn child in the womb. But immediately after birth, it is been discarded to safeguard the environment. Sometimes these organs suffer from different childish believes and rituals it is been subjected to, in different parts of the world. The construction of the first digester to decompose placentas in 2010, perhaps could be an alternative means of channeling placentas. It is clear that the placenta as used previously to generate biogas is a good substrate to serve that purpose. However, in most cases, its number (however few) is supplemented by food and other waste from the hospital. It is presumed that the reduction in the number of placentas taken home for burial rituals, would increase the number of available placentas that can be utilized in this area.

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Actively participated in:					
Conceptualization		X			
Formal Analysis	X				
Acquisition of Funds	X				
Research					X
Methodology			X		
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Means				X	
Writing-original draft		X			
Writing-revision and editing					X
Discussion of Result	X				
Review and approval of the final version		X	X		

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